

Continuous fiber reinforced RIM Nylon Composites

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Abstract

In order to overcome some difficulties in production the continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites, the RIM (Reaction Injection Molding) method was applied to the production using nylon-6 as the thermoplastics, and glass or carbon fiber as the reinforcing material. The RIM Nylon Composites thus produced were compared with continuous fiber reinforced epoxy resin composites on several physical properties.

Test results showed that the RIM Nylon Composites were superior to the epoxy resin composites, particularly in terms of impact resistance and vibration damping efficiency.

1. Introduction

In recent years, research and development of thermoplastics reinforced with continuous fiber have become active to overcome problems inherent to thermosetting resin family, especially its fragility under impact. For acceding to such a requirement, PEEK and PI reinforced by continuous fiber have been developed and its excellent performances attract a good deal of public attention.

However, there are rare case that these composites are realized of instances for practical application, due to those ploblems i.e. they require heating up the temperature of melting or softening points, and a high processing pressure also. these difficulties in the processing are yet to be solved and very few practical instances are known.

It is said that nylon resin has high impact resistance property, and short fiber reinforced nylon is used for many products by means of injection molding. However, as reinforcing fiber is short, the improvement of properties are rather poor.

In this study, we have produced structures of thermoplastic, nylon-6, reinforced by continuous fiber, glass or carbon, with the use of RIM(Reaction Injection molding) method.

We previously presented the results of studies concerning the propeties of RIM Nylon Composites reinforced with continuous carbon fiber⁽¹⁾ and its application to tennis racket frames⁽²⁾.

In this paper, we compare the glass fiber reinforced composites with carbon fiber reinforced composites, and the RIM Nylon Composites with epoxy resin composites, especially for impact resistance property and vibration dumping efficiency.

2. Experimental

2-1 Specimens

A mixture of monomer(ϵ -caprolactum), catalyst and polymerization initiator (Grade No. UX-21 of Ube Industries Ltd.)⁽³⁾ was used as the matrix resin. Glass fiber woven plain cloth(Grade No. WEA 18K 105 BZ of Nitto Boseki Co.,Ltd.) and carbon fiber woven plain

cloth (Grade No. W-3101 of Toho Rayon Co.) were used for the reinforcement.

The manufacturing process is so called S-RIM (Structural RIM) method. (4) The glass or carbon cloths was preset in the mold and then matrix monomer was injected for polymerization to make the fiber reinforced composites (GF/RIM Nylon or CF/RIM Nylon).

The epoxy resin reinforced by continuous glass or carbon fiber (GF/EP or CF/EP) used for the reference are made from the glass fiber prepreg manufactured by Nitto Boseki Co., Ltd. (Grade No. WE 18K EG C) and carbon fiber prepreg (W-3101/Q112) manufactured by Toho Rayon Co. Ltd.

The average volume content of fiber was approximately 50vol% and the specimens were conditioned at 23°C and 55%RH for more than 48hr. Specimen sizes for each test are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Specimen size

Test	length	width	thickness
Impact resistance	38	38	2
Vibration damping	145	30	4
Flexural properties	100	15	4
Abrasion resistance	102	102	4
Kinetic friction	63.5	63.5	4

Unit:mm

2-2 Test methods

2-2-1 Impact resistance

Impact test was conducted on an instrumented falling weight impact tester as shown in Fig.1 according to ASTM-D3763.

Test conditions are as follows.

Plunger velocity : 3.33m/sec.

Plunger dia. : ϕ 6.4mm

Weight : 12.1kg

- 1:Weight
- 2:Load Cell
- 3:Guide Bar
- 4:Plunger
- 5:Specimen
- 6:Fixture

Fig.1 The instrumented falling weight impact tester

2-2-2 Vibration Damping

Vibration Damping property was evaluated with the instrument as shown in Fig.2 and using Equation 1.

- 1: Specimen
- 2: Accelerometer
- 3: Impact Hammer
- 4: Amplifier
- 5: FFT Analyzer

Fig.2 The instrument of vibration damping test
 F is the force measured by the impact hammer.
 α is the acceleration measured by the accelerometer.

$$\zeta = \frac{1}{2\pi(n-1)} \ln \frac{X_1}{X_n} \quad (1)$$

Where ζ is damping ratio calculated from the logarithmic decrement.

2-2-3 Bending test

Flexural strength and modulus were measured in accordance with JIS K7055.

2-2-4 Abrasion resistance and kinetic coefficient of friction

Abrasion resistance was measured in accordance with ASTM D1044, and kinetic coefficient of friction was measured according to ASTM D1894.

3 Results And Discussion

3-1 Impact Resistance

Fig.3 shows the load-deflection and energy-deflection curves, and calculated results therefrom are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Results of impact tests

	Unit	GF/RIM Nylon	GF/EP	CF/RIM Nylon	CF/EP
Maximum Puncture Load	N	2960	2810	3810	3670
Energy to max. Puncture Load	J	4.7	3.9	5.6	3.4
Deflection at max. Puncture Load	mm	6.3	2.2	5.2	2.1
Total Energy to Puncture	J	14.2	9.9	10.5	7.5
Total Deflection to Puncture	mm	8.1	5.7	7.3	5.1

It is shown by Fig.3 and Table 2 that maximum puncture load of RIM Nylon Composite was nearly equal to that of epoxy resin composite. The puncture deflection of RIM Nylon Composite was larger than epoxy resin composite. Consequently, large energy was necessary to break RIM Nylon Composite, which seems to be derived from RIM Nylon matrix.

On the other hand, the comparison between GFRP and CFRP, maximum puncture load of GFRP was smaller than that of CFRP. But total energy to puncture of the former was larger than the latter. Particularly GF/RIM Nylon required the largest energy to puncture among the specimens compared. Considering the lower price of glass fiber than that of carbon fiber, GF/RIM Nylon seems to be more suitable for products of protectors against impact, for example, helmet, bumper beam, and so on.

(a) GF/RIM Nylon

(b) GF/epoxy

(c) CF/RIM Nylon

(d) CF/epoxy

Fig.3 Load-deflection curve and energy deflection curve of impact test for RIM Nylon Composites and epoxy resin composites

3-2 Vibration Damping Performance

Fig. 4 shows the vibration damping properties of RIM Nylon Composite and epoxy resin composite, wherein the acceleration levels(α) are plotted as the functions of time after impact.

The calculated results Employing equation 1 by FFT analyzer are shown in Table 3.

Fig. 4 Comparison of acceleration measured by vibration test

Table 3 Damping ratio calculated from logarithmic decrement measured by vibration tests

	Unit	GF/RIM Nylon	GF/EP	CF/RIM Nylon	CF/EP
Damping ratio	%	1.38	0.66	0.82	0.44

Fig.4 and Table 3 show that the values of damping ratio of RIM Nylon Composites were double as large as those of epoxy resin composites, which indicate the excellent performance of RIM Nylon Composite in vibration damping efficiency.

On the other hand, when GFRP and CFRP are compared, the values of damping ratio for GFRP were larger than those of CFRP. Particularly GF/RIM Nylon was the best in vibration damping property among these test samples.

To take advantage of this property, GF/RIM Nylon will be best suited for sporting goods, for example, a tennis racket frame, bicycle parts, and so on.

3-3 Other Characteristics

RIM Nylon Composite proved to have excellent flexural strength and modulus, excellent slidability ; these are other advantages of this composite.

3-3-1 Flexural Strength and Modulus

Results of flexural tests were as shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Results of flexural tests

	Unit	GF/RIM Nylon	GF/EP	CF/RIM Nylon	CF/EP
Flexural Strength	MPa	470	490	800	800
Flexural Modulus	GPa	25	26	55	56

Table 4 shows that RIM Nylon Composite was almost equivalent to epoxy resin composite regarding flexural strength and modulus.

3-3-2 Slidability

Results of measurement regarding abrasion and kinetic coefficient of friction were as shown in Table 5.

Table 5 Results of abrasion tests and the measurements of kinetic coefficient of friction

	Unit	GF/RIM Nylon	GF/EP	CF/RIM Nylon	CF/EP
Abrasion loss	mg	23	80	14	48
Kinetic coefficient of friction	—	0.23	0.27	0.23	0.31

Table 5 shows that RIM Nylon Composite had better abrasion resistance than epoxy resin composite, and the kinetic coefficient of friction, for RIM Nylon Composite was smaller than that of epoxy resin composite.

In other words, RIM Nylon Composite is excellent in slidability.

4. Conclusion

The characteristics of RIM Nylon Composite reinforced by continuous glass or carbon fiber were compared with those of epoxy resin composite.

From this study, the following conclusions are reached:

1. RIM Nylon Composite has excellent impact resistance compared with epoxy resin composite.
2. RIM Nylon Composite has excellent vibration damping property compared with epoxy resin composite.
3. GFRP is excellent in impact resistance and in vibration damping property compared with CFRP. GF/RIM Nylon is most excellent in impact resistance and in vibration damping property among the samples of this study. Therefore GF/RIM Nylon will best suited for protector against impact or sporting goods.
4. RIM Nylon Composite is almost equivalent to epoxy resin composite in terms of flexural strength and modulus.
5. RIM Nylon Composite has excellent slidability.

5. References

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